

A Locally Spherical GRT predicts Quantum Spin Dynamics, QSD, where Time is A Dynamic Relativistic Aether or the Singularity, Linking GRT, Loop Quantum Gravity & String theory

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Abstract

The emergence of General Relativity examined via a Dynamic Spin Metric, DSM, predicts that OUR 1-sphere Universe exists as de-Sitter space on the Manifold of the Super-singularity presenting as a Space-time singularity with an effective relativistic radius of Gyration of R_{eff} , {electron uncertainty of $\Delta x \geq R_{eff}/2$ (known p) and $\Delta x \geq R_{eff}$ for the Space-time Aether, (analogous to the loops in LQG linked by time via R_{eff})} This imposes a maximum quiescent curvature of space-time of $1/R_{eff}$ in flat space OR $1/R_{eff}^2$ at the first Big Bang or $1/|\ell_p|R_{eff}$ or $1/|\ell_p|^2 R_{eff}^2$ on a super-singularity's manifold as Space-time which are remnants of 2 entangled Black and White holes or an EPR Gray hole. The particle singularities Wedge Sum contains, in faciem suam, the laws of the Universe as well as Black Energy, or zero energy photons, and Black Matter (form, anti-form matter), and exist on the manifold of the 4 sphere, anti-Desitter space, Core, and present as the Electric and Magnetic Fields on the singularity firewall contained within the event Horizon of quantum particles as predicted by GRT. The space inside R_{eff} is elastic empty space with a coefficient of quantum elasticity of $k_A = m_e C^2 / (2R_{eff})^2$; $E_p = k_A (h_n R_{eff} \wedge h_{nk} R_{eff})$; $h_n = 2,4,6$ for QSD harmonics of the electron, up and down quark respectively and artifacts of the defining metric $\sum_1^n \mathbf{LET} \overline{\mathbf{AB}}_i = \mathbf{Ct}_j + \mathbf{R}_{rap} v$, where n is the number of Black Photon particles, each having a quiescent entangled energy, of $(3/4)m_e C^2$ and coupled to the electric field via α . The value of C and R_{rap} provide the carrier frequency, ω , of OUR Holographic Universe and the resultant harmonics, where half spin and full spin particles are even and odd harmonics respectively. When point particles are modelled as mini black-holes $R_{eff} \rightarrow R_s$, and space inside the event horizon and above R_{eff} becomes 4 sphere in a quaternion metric space, governed by a 4D phase-wave $\Psi_{ijkR} = \exp[i\omega t] \cdot \exp[j\omega t] \cdot \exp[k\omega t] \cdot \exp[-\omega t] = |\ell_p|$ at the first Big Bang, while the empty space inside the singularity of the black and white hole is entangled via a single dimension $\overline{\mathbf{AB}}_{ijk} = \mathbf{Ct}_j + \mathbf{R}_{eff}$, or the ER=EPR link and provides a new dimension of gravity via the uncertainty principal for string theory. The properties of the singularity are a function of R_{eff}/h_n ; $h_n = 1$ for space-time. A CHSH experiment will confirm the geometry of nothing within the singularity of R_{eff} by altering the location of the origin of the singularity relative to THE Universe and establish it as the third observer in quantum interactions.

1.0 Introduction

As Einstein often pondered "what is time?" In DSM and QSD time is everything while j spin is the time of ticking clocks and i, k spin are the harmonics and complex time, that present as matter. Within the math of Loop Quantum Gravity it does not exist, yet in a colloquial sense, time is the essence of both Serendipity and Fatum [1], (*Serendipity* \wedge *Fatum*), or the resultant dimension of Consciousness in a Universe forced by a let statement so powerful that it creates everything from nothing, yet so gentle that it also forces life and resultantly Freewill. Further we will demonstrate that Serendipity is likely the Will of the Universe entangled in some perverse dance with Freewill, or (*FreeWill* \wedge *UniversalWill*). The Will of THE Universe exists inside the entangled black and white hole or EPR Gray Hole, void of time and presents as the core of OUR Universe. Free Will

exists as uncertainty within the singularity of the electron of $\Delta x \geq R_{eff}/2$ and $\Delta x \geq R_{eff}$ within space time or the relativistic Aether and further contained within the event Horizon Core of the entangled EPR Gray Hole or $\Delta x \geq R_g$ in the Schwarzschild metric. It is this conformal boundary that consists of plastically deformed space created during the Big Bangs that separates the quantum world of anti-deSitter space contained within the singularity that presents as the point particle or wedge sum, WS, and deSitter space or the macroscopic world above the atomic manifold.[2] Using the mass of Dark energy of 8.8×10^{84} electron masses, the change in radius of the Void of THE Universe is $\partial R = 8.8 \times 10^{84} \times 4 \ell_p^2 / R_{eff} = 2.51693091 \times 10^{12}$ light years of the 4 sphere Void or Super Singularity. Calculating ∂R for the 4 sphere manifold $(2.51693091 \times 10^{12})^{75} \times 2\pi = 12.6 \times 10^9$ or 12.6 billion light years and this would be the age of OUR

Universe if it was empty which distills to $\Delta x \geq R_g$ or $R_g = 2.51693091 \times 10^{12} m$ in 4 sphere space or $R_g = 2.2718137 \times 10^9$, and about 14.3 billion using the current estimate of ordinary matter. The uncertainty of OUR Universe or the Void singularity is currently $8.8 \times 10^{84} \times 4 \frac{e_p^2}{R_{eff}}$ or about $9.19522639 \times 10^{15} \times \hbar$ or $9.19522639 \times 10^{15}$ times larger than the uncertainty of space-time or 1.8×10^{16} times the uncertainty of the electron or $3550.8m$, while the uncertainty of more massive particles decreases and likely converges onto a deterministic 1 sphere de Sitter Universe. The gravitational constant of the EPR Gray Hole at the first instance was about 10^{70} times that of current G and abated to the G of OUR Current Universe at 19.24637272 seconds after the first Big Bang and is diminishing as OUR Universe ages increasing the dispersion of the Aether or space-time.

If we constrain our definition as the passage of time, we can envision it as grains of sand contained within an hour glass, the grains on the top are potential time and the grains below are spent time or the past. If we further imagine this hour glass to be perfectly conical we arrive at relativistic Minkowski space time, or a compactified time. If we view orthogonal time as complex time, we can see that this time exists in 2 dimension's relative to the one dimensional time we see on ticking clocks. With respect to matter we noted that an i spin and k spin of time created the harmonic masses, Table 1 and Table 2, for the standard table of elementary particles. Much like energy is stored mathematically orthogonal in a capacitor or inductor, time is stored in complex time as owned by the Aether, presenting as matter. Within we will show that time does not stop at the event horizon but becomes complex time as it propagates orthogonally. If we further understand it in terms of the mathematics of Eventology or the probabilistic events of consciousness, and view time as the underpinning of topology, we can see how the probability of events to occur converges at the wedge sum, WS, that we experience as the present, and reduces to a single probability of 1 when it exists in the fleeting moment of the present or the hypersurface of a locally present.

As potential time encroaches on the present, the number of possible future events distills, to manifest itself as the present. We can view the origin in Minkowski space as the wedge sum, WS, the discontinuity between the past and present, given that the failure of time to propagate along the arrow of time, forces the creation of matter as time spins about the manifold of space time or the Aether, hence providing the benchmarks for space, an orthogonal dimension to time in Minkowski. In DSM, complex time is orthogonal from the DSM metric $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 + jCt^2 = 0$. What the human experience of time reveals, is that the passage of this potential makes its resource more valuable and upon the gasping of our last breathe, almost always generates a concern as to whether it was time well spent.

Fatum can be understood as the laws of the Universe set in place by the let statement and defined by THE Space that does not exist in OUR Universe and contained within the manifold of

the space-time singularity AKA the particle Aether with an effective radius, R_{eff} . When the locally flat space of Minkowski space is made locally spherical, this space becomes matter. Its Serendipitous nature is contained within the manifold of defined reality by R_{eff} and presents in OUR Universe as $\Delta x \geq R_{eff}/2$ (for a known p) from the uncertainty principal of the electron.

When the origin of Minkowski space is modelled as a locally spherical entangled White and Black hole of a Brane and Anti-brane, the White hole moves forwards in time at $\frac{1}{2} C$ and the Black hole moves backwards in time at $\frac{1}{2} C$, creating a perfect symmetry in both space and time about the singularity contained within the event horizon that acts as a firewall via strong force, between OUR Universe and THE Universe which presents as THE singularity contained within where $\sum E_\infty = 0$ or the sum of everything equals nothing. This firewall is the event horizon of the singularity as defined by the first Big Bang.

Fig 1 Minkowski time

Although DSM makes quantum deterministic from a Why perspective, OUR inability to know when we are observing, or sampling these events known as quantum states, will always be obscured by the uncertainty principal, and the best we will ever be able to comprehend Freewill is governed by this principal. But this paper is to understand time from a math perspective and possibly shine a quasi-light on the matter of time, with mathematical consistency as it pertains to GRT. By modeling point particles, PP, as mini black holes, the passage of time ceases at the event horizon, or $\partial\tau = 0$, so it is reasonable to model matter as complex time and the end of REAL proper time. Within we will see how the 4 sphere geometry within the event horizon we use GRT to predict quantum and use Bekenstein-Hawking entropy to predict the 4 sphere structure of the core of OUR Universe and OUR Universe as a finite, continuous medium on it's manifold.

1.1 Quantum Spin Dynamics

Unlike two of QSD's subsets, Loop Quantum Gravity, LQG and String Theory, QSD is defined by time such that the passage of time exists in the j direction, $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 + jCt^2 = 0$, when j spin is demodulated and mass exists in complex time, such that harmonics in i, k create "quasi loops" or "quasi springs" of compressed space. See Fig 3. Time is wound in i and k relativistically about the singularity R_{eff}/h_n where h_n is the harmonic and conserves angular momentum and G is a function

of the harmonic, $G_{h_n} = h_n \frac{(C)^2 |\ell_p|^2}{R_{eff} m_e}$. This explains the conformal boundary relationship between G and the gravitational force beneath the atomic manifold as a function of a phantom centripetal force, where $G \propto h_n$ or above the atomic manifold of $G_N = N \frac{(C)^2 |\ell_p|^2}{R_{eff} m_e}$ where N is the number of electron masses.

While in LQG the "gravity" loops present as finite loops and piece wise continuous as they move through time, they are "spring" continuous when viewed from the perspective of j spin in QSD while they are piece wise continuous from the perspective of the true Holographic nature of OUR Universe and the interior of the Helix is anti-DE sitter space, while the exterior is DE sitter space and the sample rate is a function of the uncertainty principal. It is noteworthy that as mass increases with harmonics, h_n , uncertainty decreases such that $\Delta x \geq R_{eff}/h_n$ beginning with the second harmonic of 2 for the electron.

The first Big Bang evolving from the metric $\overline{AB}_i = Ct_j + R_{rap}i$ or the relativistic $\overline{AB}_{ik} = Ct_j + R_{eff}ik$ created full spin particles or "gravitational" space-time when the 4D phase wave forced maximum compression of elastic space-time:

$$\Psi_{ijkR} = \exp[i\omega t] \cdot \exp[j\omega t] \cdot \exp[k\omega t] \cdot \exp[-R\omega t] = |\ell_p|;$$

LQG predicts a collapse of a pre-existing Universe, and QSD predicts a collapse of empty space or THE Universe and creates Dark Energy or zero energy photons from the square wave compression of space as per the Finite to Fourier Analysis in i :

$$2\pi|\ell_p|_i \cdot R_{RAP_i} = 8|\ell_p|_i R_{RAP_i} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)} \sin\left(\frac{(2n-1)C}{R_{RAP}}\right) \#, \#(1a)$$

$$2\pi|\ell_p|_i \cdot R_{RAP_i} = 8|\ell_p|_i R_{RAP_i} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)} \sin\left(\frac{-(2n-1)C}{R_{RAP}}\right) \#, \#(1b)$$

where *Eq. (1a)*, is Brane A in DSM and becomes the *FORM_i* and *Eq. (1b)*, is Brane B in DSM and becomes the *ANTI-FORM_i*. Interestingly, the series sums to zero but generates the square wave for the Form, and the 180-degree phase shifted square wave of the ANTI-FORM. This symmetry in time, predicts what science currently terms the anti-particle.

Finite to Fourier Analysis in k

$$2\pi|\ell_p|_k \cdot R_{RAP_k} = 8|\ell_p|_k R_{RAP_k} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)} \sin\left(\frac{(2n-1)C}{R_{RAP}}\right) \#, \#(5.2.1a)$$

$$2\pi|\ell_p|_k \cdot R_{RAP_k} = 8|\ell_p|_k R_{RAP_k} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n-1)} \sin\left(\frac{-(2n-1)C}{R_{RAP}}\right) \#, \#(5.2.1b)$$

where *Eq. (1a)*, is Brane A in DSM and becomes the *FORM_k* and *Eq. (1b)*, is Brane B in DSM and becomes the *ANTI-FORM_k*.

The second Big Bang was a compression of space of a saw-toothed wave and created half spin particles. We start with analysis in i , or R_{RAP_i} . Relying on the infinite series developed by Fourier, we start with a compression of space in the i basis, by $|\ell_p|_i \cdot R_{RAP_i}$, or the element in i . The Blaszyński cube can be thought of as the partial differential, $\partial_{e_1} \partial_{e_2} \partial_{e_3}$, of the Glowney cube.[11] The geometry predicted by the Glowney Cube for

matter manifests itself as an equilateral triangle and is consistent with the geometry of the photon in DSM's flat space. Since particles exist in space-time, it is reasonable to assume them to be a function of time and space if they are to woven into the fabric of time for GRT analysis. We recall that what remains from the entire harmonic series are the even harmonics, for which, the saw-tooth wave has half the duty cycle; hence we arrive at:

$$2\pi t|\ell_p|_{m,n} \cdot R_{RAP_{m\wedge n}} = -8|\ell_p|_i R_{RAP_{m\wedge n}} \times \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)} \sin\left(\frac{(2n)C}{R_{RAP}}\right) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)} \sin\left(\frac{-(2n)C}{R_{RAP}}\right) \right) \#. (2a)$$

Normalizing the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ requires using 720-degrees for each spin. When we normalize, we get the saw-tooth wave expansion:

$$-8|\ell_p|_i \cdot R_{RAP_{m,n}} \times \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n)} \sin\left(\frac{(n)C}{R_{RAP}}\right) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n)} \sin\left(\frac{-(n)C}{R_{RAP}}\right) \right) \#. (2b)$$

Eq. (2a) and *Eq. (2b)* resemble the Fourier Series of a saw-tooth wave from our undergrad math class and is now consistent with the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ model of quantum. When we match the $\frac{4}{\pi}$ scalars, we also arrive at half the angular momentum of the spin 1 particles derived above. As such, the angular momentum is now half as well. Full spin particles are odd harmonics, and half spin particles are even harmonics, and Fourier predicts this when we assume the Big Bang created the harmonic series. Hence the conservation of momentum is a consequence of relativity from the perspective of THE Universe or space inside the singularity. *Table 1 & 2* clearly indicate that the predicted harmonics are also consistent with the Standard model mass predictions. Massive spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particles are the result of the even harmonics, and the following table summarizes the Chinner Cube's harmonic predictions for spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particles.

DSM Predictions of $\frac{1}{2}$ spin particle masses as EVEN Harmonics			
Harm- onic	Quark Name	Harmonic Mass Predictions	Most Recent Measurement [12]
4 th	Up	2.044 <i>Mev/C²</i>	2.2 ^{+0.5} _{-0.4} <i>Mev/C²</i>
6 th	Down	4.600 <i>Mev/C²</i>	4.7 ^{+0.5} _{-0.4} <i>Mev/C²</i> 1
28 th	Strange	100.156 <i>Mev/C²</i>	95 ⁺⁹ _{-0.3} <i>Mev/C²</i> 1
100 th	Charm	1,277 <i>Mev/C²</i>	1,275 ⁺²⁵ ₋₃₅ <i>Mev/C²</i>
180 th	Bottom	4,180 <i>Mev/C²</i>	4,180 ⁺⁴⁰ ₋₃₀ <i>Mev/C²</i>
610 th	Top	172,785 <i>Mev/C²</i>	172,760 ⁺³⁰⁰ ₋₃₀₀ <i>Mev/C²</i>
118 th	Tau electron	1778.79 <i>Mev/C²</i>	1776.86 ± .12 <i>Mev/C²</i>

Table 1 – Spin 1/2 Harmonic Masses (Note: Top as the 610th harmonic at 47535 *Mev/C²* plus the Higgs mass 125.25 ± 0.17 GeV/c² or 172.785 *GeV/C²*).

Predictions of 1,0 spin particle masses as Harmonics			
Harm onic	Boson Name	DSM Mass Predictions	Most Recent Measurement [12][13]
793 rd	W	80,335 <i>Mev/C²</i>	80,379 ⁺¹² ₋₁₂ <i>Mev/C²</i> 80,433 ⁺⁹ ₋₉ (2)
845 th	Z	91,216 <i>Mev/C²</i>	91,187.6 ^{+2.1} _{-2.1} <i>Mev/C²</i>
990 th	Higgs	125208. <i>Mev/C²</i>	125250 ± 170 <i>MeV/c²</i>

Table 2 – One and Zero-spin Harmonic Masses.
(80.379 ± 0.01291, 91.1876 ± .0021 *GeV/c*)

Note the Higgs can have various masses as a zero-spin particle. The top quark measured as the 594th harmonic at $45074 \text{ Mev}/C^2$ in 2020, in addition to the Higgs mass measured at ATLAS from 120 to $126 \text{ Gev}/C^2$, are also valid solutions to the top quark. We now believe that the Higgs can have many masses, likely correlating to the top quark harmonic since the top quark energy is quite narrowly defined.

Space inside the singularity and outside the singularity correspond to anti-Desitter space and Desitter space respectively, and are piecewise continuous about the wedge sum, WS, existing as diffeomorphisms in their respective domain. When we use a cosine correction factor derivative of the gravitational lens of plastic deformation of $1 + 2\sqrt{2}\alpha$, our quantum prediction using GRT for the Bohr radii has the same number of significant digits as G, which is the limiting factor imposed by Schwarzschild's GRT solution. Using 4sphere geometry beneath the atomic manifold and 1sphere above, Space-time can be modelled as "quasi-continuous" about the wedge sum when the gravitational lens of the plastically deformed manifold is considered. Although the zero energy photon has a mass $|2m_e|$ it is not detectable, much like a drop of water is indistinguishable from the body of water that contains it, until the photon has an energy since the fabric of space time is zero energy photons and this assumption was used to prove the 4sphere geometry of the singularity using Bekenstein-Hawking entropy and superseding a Susskind assumption in his derivation of black hole radius change per photon or $\partial R/\partial N$ given that the photon wavelength would be infinite at the event horizon given that time stops and the following falls out to the same math when we assume the quiescent photon energy $E = \frac{3}{4}m_e C^2$ of the bound anti-particle particle pair is pulled apart by the tidal forces releasing the binding energy via entangled monogamy and as such:

$$\frac{\partial R}{\partial N} = 4 \frac{\ell_p^2}{R_{eff}} \rightarrow \frac{\pi^2}{2} R_{eff}^4 \partial R = 2\pi^2 \ell_p^2 R_{eff}^3 \partial N$$

This would indicate that the change of radius of the super-singularity is a function of the 4sphere geometry while the manifold of the 4sphere is a function of ∂N or information bit.

2.0 The uncertainty of time

The genesis of time arises from $LET \overline{AB}_i = Ct_j + R_{rap} i$ where t_j defines the element of time as it further defines distance AB, however the error in distance arises as the spin forced by the let statement, has a spin radius $R_{rap} i = \frac{4}{3} R_{eff}$ as projected onto j , which defines the spin metric, DSM, or the wedge sum, WS, modelled as the event horizon for quantum particles, AKA point particles or PP's. As a first year refresher, the uncertainty principal for the electron is: $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar/2$. In lay terms the error in measuring x and p AKA position and momentum is dependent on how precisely we measure either position x or velocity of momentum of a half spin particle, which is the stuff we call matter. If we assume mass to be constant in the measuring process, which we will also show to be a construct of time, therefore $\Delta x \Delta x/t \geq \hbar/2$, and if x is known the error is imposed on time, Δt .

This means that when we try to observe or understand the space and time continuum, we are only allowed to know one correctly at any given sample time. As a side note the error on space time in DSM, was shown to be $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar$. Further when we impose a rigid value on space, we induce a measured error on time. This was demonstrated to be the path around the effective radius of the PP radius and $R_{eff}/2$ for the event horizon or effective electron radius that exists in THE Universe. It can be assumed that the same error exists in space and time for higher energy particles as mass increases inversely proportionately as a function of R_{eff}/N , where N is the harmonic.

We will show that mass is a function of time, in fact harmonics, so the issue as to whether mass or time has a measured error imposed upon it is an issue of semantics, however it is clear that the carrier frequency of OUR Universe is ($\sim 10^{20} \text{ Hz}$ from the let statement, $\omega = C/R_{rap}$ or $f = C/2\pi R_{rap}$ and it's cut-off frequency of $2.615960949 \times 10^{19} \text{ Hz}$, exists just below 3db cutoff point of Hard Xray, $3 \times 10^{19} \text{ Hz}$).

2.1 Geometric time; a matter of time

The geometry of periodicity can be understood when we look at how higher dimensional geometries impose a time element on the observers space. If we take a circle and view it in 1D, the user must observe this circle as a function of time. We assume time to start as the circle moves upwards through the one dimensional slot of the 'math' toaster. As it is sampled or appears to exist along the mouth of the toaster, the length of the round toast starts at zero and maximises at its diameter as it rises with time and then reduces back to zero as it exits the mouth of the toaster. When viewed from above or in 'plane' sight, the line appears, grows, shrinks, and then disappears as Susskind's cookie is snatched for consumption during class as forbidden by his wife.

A 3sphere in 2D is much the same as the sphere moves through the 2D Universe, the toaster mouth existing in 2D now, the sphere exists as a dot then a growing circle, then shrinking and then disappearing.

A 4 sphere is much the same in 3D. The dot at the origin that would need to exist as a WS and would grow into an ever increasing sphere until it approached an infinite size and then it would shrink back to a dot in idealized space. It is spherical space that induces periodicity into OUR Universe as witnessed by higher dimensional geometry existing in lower dimensions and it is the spherical space predicted by DSM that explains the wave nature of matter, presenting as spin based, from quantum to the cosmos. The Caveat and the brilliance of the let statement that constricts this size of the sphere, is the constancy of C and when this speed limit is further imposed onto quantum spins, this max size is limited by the maximum compression of elastic physical space of $|\ell_p|$ and the REAL dimension of the 4 sphere is:

$$\Psi_{ijkR} = \exp[i\omega t] \cdot \exp[j\omega t] \cdot \exp[k\omega t] \cdot \exp[-R\omega t] = |\ell_p|$$

Since $i\wedge j\wedge\hat{k}$ is orthogonal to the manifold, R exists upon the manifold of the phase wave. In some applications a counter clockwise spin in R may provide the perspective of looking at OUR Universe from the outside or THE Universe.

In essence, this constricts this 4D phase wave to a single dimension at the first Big Bang, BB, such that space in THE empty Universe is compressed to $|\ell_p|R_{rap}$, plus a small compression, that presents as plastic deformation. It is the speed limit that imposes the harmonics of matter from $|\ell_p| \rightarrow CEM$, Center of Energy Mass, (AKA The Higgs Boson in 1D, Quantum Foam, space-time or Aether) and presenting as the wave nature of matter of this 4 sphere of compressed physical space, undulating in OUR Universe, whilst it spins according to Newton's vision, about this radius of nothing in THE Universe. This equation was shown to predict the mass of the neutron and proton with errors well within the measured values of Codata 2018. The same analogy likely exists when the higher dimensional quarks living in Octonion space pass through the quaternion based DSM of the 4 sphere and this assumption predicted the effective radius of the up and down quarks. Since the Let statement is responsible for creating the centripetal force to induce spin, another phantom force, G, manifests itself on the surface of the spin manifold or space time singularity,

$$G = C^2 |\ell_p|^2 / (R_{eff} m_e).$$

2.2 A locally spherical GRT predicts Quantum

When point particles, PP's are modelled as mini black holes in DSM, a locally spherical spin metric, GRT predicts quantum. What we see as the electron cloud is actually quantum blur as the electron is smeared about the manifold of the spherical event horizon by huge tidal forces, $G/|\ell_p|^2$. These are a function of the effective radius of the singularity, $1/R_{eff}$ in flat space, or $1/R_{eff}^2$ on the manifold, and presents as the quiescent maximum curvature of Space Time, creating a firewall about the singularity. When the relativistic force of repulsion was calculated in flat space and was found to be the anti-strong force:

$$\frac{24\sqrt{2}(\sqrt{3}/2R_{rap})C^2}{\pi^4 r^2} m_e (2.5096)$$

And predicted 100.01% of the Coulomb force when the cosine effect and effective radius of electron is considered:

$$\frac{24\sqrt{2}(\sqrt{3}/2R_{rap})C^2}{(1+\alpha)\left(\frac{1}{\alpha}+1\right)\pi^4 r^2} m_e \times 2.509675293$$

It also predicts time as the entangled white and black holes, where \overline{AB}_i is the only metric inside the otherwise empty but elastic space created by $\overline{AB}_i = Ct_j + R_{rap} i$ or $\overline{AB}_{ik} = Ct_j + R_{eff} ik$ in 3D, where the energy mass of quantum particles is a function of $R_{eff} i/n$, n being the harmonic and energy mass is stored via elastic compression. $R_{eff} i$ or the radius of the singularity. Beyond the radius of the singularity, space is a spherical spin metric and the $T_{\mu\nu}$ tensor is better understood as the energy

density, modelled as $\rho(r) \rightarrow \rho(2N/\pi^2 r^4)$, where N is the number of/ or the electron mass equivalence per 4 sphere density in a Quaternion spin space. This defines space between the singularity and the event horizon, AKA the atomic manifold, as a 4D spin metric where GRT predicts the event horizon as the classical electron radius, the quark radii (when extrapolated to an Octonion spin metric space) relative to the Aether of time, AKA space-time and the Bohr radii as the event horizon relative to the proton.

Physical Constants as a function of R_{eff}		
Descriptor		Derived values
Effective radius of point particles	R_{eff}	$R_{eff} = \frac{3}{4} R_{rap} = 3.861592679 \times 10^{-13}$
Gravitational	G	$\frac{(C)^2 \ell_p ^2}{R_{eff} m_e} = 6.6742998 \times 10^{-11}$
Quantized G	G_N	$\frac{(\ell_p C)^2}{R_{eff}} N^2 = J_B (nC)^2 **$
Reduced Planck	\hbar	$m_e C R_{eff} = 1.0545718175 \dots \times 10^{-34}$
Fine Structure	α	$R_{eff}/a_0 = 7.297352568 \times 10^{-3}$
Bohr radius	a_0	$\frac{R_{eff}}{\alpha} = 5.29177210855 \times 10^{-11}$
Classical electron Radius	r_e	$R_{eff} \alpha = \left(\frac{R_{eff}^2}{a_0}\right) = 2.8179403260 \times 10^{-15}$
Rydberg constant	R_∞	$\frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{R_{eff}}{a_0^2} = 10973731.567181$
Schwarzschild radius (EH predicts BB)	$R_s \rightarrow R_{sBB}$	$\frac{2\ell_p^2 N}{(R_{eff})} = \frac{2(i\ell_p \cdot R_{eff} \wedge \hat{k} \ell_p \cdot R_{eff})N}{iR_{eff} \wedge jR_{eff} \wedge \hat{k}R_{eff}}$
Electron Mass	m_e	$\frac{ \ell_p ^2 C^2}{G R_{eff}} = 9.10938 (xx)$
Chinner's Constant	J_B	$\frac{\ell_p^2}{(R_{eff})} = 6.76477413 \times 10^{-58} \frac{m}{M^2} ****$
Electric Field/ $\partial\tau$	$e^2 Z_c i$	$(3/4)m_e C^2 \alpha$ (Quantum)
Magnetic Field/ ∂S	$e^2 Z_L \hat{k}$	$m_e 4\pi(\sqrt{3}/2R_{rap})^2 \alpha$ (Quantum)
Coulomb Force (EM Force)	$ F_p $	$\frac{24\sqrt{2}(\sqrt{3}/2R_{rap})C^2}{(1+\alpha)\left(\frac{1}{\alpha}+1\right)\pi^4 r^2} m_e (2.5096)$
Compton Wavelength	λ_e	$2\pi R_{eff} = 2.42631023867(73) \times 10^{-12}$
Coefficient of Elasticity (Quantum)	k_A	$m_e C^2 / 2R_{eff}^2; E_p = \frac{k_A}{2} (\hbar_n R_{eff} \wedge \hbar_n R_{eff}) ***$
Black hole area	A	$16\pi (N \ell_p^2 / R_{eff})^2 N = M/m_e$
R/N	∂R	$4(\ell_p^2 / R_{eff}) \partial N = 4J_B \partial N$

Table 3

This metric assumes particles spin at C and the quantum radii are the escape radii for $\partial\tau = 0$. On this atomic manifold time becomes massive and complex as it spins about the event horizon and presents as matter. The carrier frequency of OUR Universe is a function of $\omega t = Ct_j / R_{eff} i$ and these are the oscillations of a lower-dimensional black-hole horizon that OUR consciousness demodulates with i and k spins as artifact's manifesting as the electric field and the magnetic field that Susskind can see.

Gravity can be quantised at a quantum level given that all quantum particles are merely harmonics so it is in fact REAL spin that is quantised.

The laws of OUR Universe manifest themselves on the manifold of the singularity as the 4D phase wave experiences a “gravitational lensing” beneath the atomic manifold to exit this 4D quantum reality to emerge as the carrier frequency of the hologram via $\mathcal{L}^+ = i \wedge j \wedge k$ plus $\mathcal{L}^- = -i \wedge -j \wedge -k = Ct$.

Although \overline{AB}_i is fixed within the singularity, the j spin forces $\overline{AB}_j = Ct$, such that the Brane moves forward in time at $Cj/2$ and the anti-brane moves backwards at $Cj/2$ or Universe and parallel Universe respectively in Kruskal-Szekeres diagrams Fig 4, and the A and B exist as the white hole and black hole in i . The Penrose diagram can be compactified such that $\mathcal{L}^+ = i \wedge j \wedge k$ plus $\mathcal{L}^- = -i \wedge -j \wedge -k = Ct$ and Kruskal-Szekeres diagram can be better understood where the white hole and black hole are entangled in space as per $\overline{AB}_i = R_{eff i}$ or the Einstein-Rosen bridge yet $\overline{AB}_j = Ct$ as it spirals up the conformal boundary in anti-Desitter space and this entanglement creates what we perceive as the Laws of OUR Universe as a function of the effective radius of the singularity in Table 3, while the Universe and Parallel Universe in Kruskal-Szekeres Fig 2 and fig 3, are governed by $\overline{AB}_j = Ct$. This also may explain why an evaporating Black hole can be entangled with radiation at the extremes of OUR Universe since the center of the singularity is fixed and common to all space-time as the Einstein-Rosen bridge spins about the center of the singularity creating a firewall which coincidentally is anti-strong force, which the author calculated to be the same magnitude as Strong force [4]. Hence the anti-strong force prevents OUR Universe from collapsing back into THE Universe which is contained within the singularity, where the outside exists within us when one visualizes the fixed radius in i and the spin outward in an orthogonal j spin.

FIG 2 Kruskal-Szekeres diagram

The conformal boundary of anti-de Sitter space, Fig 3, can be thought of as the helical boundary between OUR Universe and THE Universe or the space-time manifold and the phantom force of G is an artifact of the let statement, $LET \overline{AB}_i = Ct_j + R_{rap i}$ at the first Big Bang and maximum elastic compression of $|\ell_p|$, since this let statement forces j spin requiring an implied force to

maintain the circular motion. Delocalization is likely an artifact of common center of spin for every space-time particle, given $\overline{AB}_{ik} = R_{eff ik}$ and its spin about O or the center of the singularity. When examined discreetly the Helix can be modelled as a stack of hyperbolic discs separated in the j direction or time direction by the uncertainty principal and carrier $\omega_0 = C/R_{eff i}$. Examining the Helix using GRT in an analog continuum, will add resolution to the quantum blur and make quantum deterministic, from a pedagogical perspective. The conformal boundary in Fig 3 can be thought of as the helical boundary between OUR Universe and THE Universe or the space-time manifold and the phantom force of G is an artifact of the let statement, $LET \overline{AB}_i = Ct_j + R_{rap i}$, since this let statement forces j spin requiring an implied force to maintain the circular motion.

FIG 3 LQG loops as “springs” Helically wound conformal boundary

The quantum event horizons predicted by a first order model of GRT in quantum are about 2.5% higher than Codata values, but this is expected given the plastic deformation of the Bangs that sealed the elastic space of THE Universe inside PP’s, the effective radius of the proton as a function of charge radius of $8.4075 \times 10^{-16}m$ and the lensing of the compressed space and further given $\lim r(\rho)_{\rho=0} = 1 + \rho^2/4$. Note ρ is not energy density but the value used by Susskind when the event horizon is normalised to 1 and ρ is the distance beyond the event horizon. A higher resolution understanding of plastic deformation can be realised by normalising the effective radius of the singularity or $R_{eff i}$ to 1 and I leave this as an exercise to smart people like Susskind. When the cosine effect is considered in a second order model of the Schwarzschild metric or $(1 + 2\sqrt{2}\alpha)$, the Bohr radii is accurate to the same number of significant digits as G in Codata 2018, G being the limiting accuracy factor in GRT for quantum space-time. The Classical radius of the electron and Bohr radii are found using GRT in a spherical space using a quantized Schwarzschild assuming arc length ds .

$$ds^2 = -(1 - 2J_B N/r)C^2 dt^2 + (1 - 2J_B N/r)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2) \quad |ds|^2 = |di|^2 + |dk|^2; \quad i \perp k$$

The Classical electron radius or particle spin above the space-time singularity, where arc length, ds is an infinite number of orthogonal steps $ds^2 = di \cdot dk = g(di, dk); i \perp k$ [14]:

$$r = 2\ell_p^2 N / R_{eff} = 2J_B = 2 \times 6.76477413 \times 10^{-58}$$

$$(i+k): \pi^2 r_e^4 / 2 = 2 (6.76477413 \times 10^{-58}); |(i+k)| = \sqrt{2}$$

$$|i+k| r_e = 4.06914707 \times 10^{-15}$$

$$r_e = 4.06914707 \times 10^{-15} \div \sqrt{2} = 2.87732149 \times 10^{-15}$$

$$r_e = 2.87732149 \times 10^{-15} / (1 + 2\sqrt{2}\alpha) = 2.81913447 \times 10^{-15}$$

Electron Orbit about proton:

$$r_{z,\mu} = (m_e/\mu)(a_0/Z)$$

$$: (\pi^2/2) \cdot ((i+k)\alpha^2 Zr)_{a_0}^4 = (6.76477413 \times 10^{-58}); |(i+k)| = \sqrt{2}$$

$$a_0 = 4.06914707 \times 10^{-15} \div \sqrt{2}\alpha^2 = 5.4004447 \times 10^{-11} m.$$

$$= 5.4004447 \times 10^{-11} / (1 + 2\sqrt{2}\alpha) = 5.291233483 \times 10^{-11}$$

These correspond to 2018 Codata values of $2.817\ 940\ 3262(13) \times 10^{-15} \times 0.9995764147$ and $5.291800814 \times 10^{-11} m \times 0.9998927906$ or 5.291233483 and 0.9998927906 respectively given the cosine effect error correction of $1 + 2\sqrt{2}\alpha$ predicts these orbit radii to the same number of significant digits as G given its current Codata 2018 value $6.67430(15) \times 10^{-11}$. It is note worthy that adding the charge radius to the Bohr radii we get $5.291317483 \times 10^{-11} m$ which is 0.9999086642 the Codata value. Up Quark N=4; $3.98516943 \times 10^{-15} \times \alpha^2 = 2.1221567 \times 10^{-19} m$ Down Quark N=9; $2.59910053 \times 10^{-19} m$; both $< 4.3 \times 10^{-19}$, the upper limit on the effective quark radius (95% C.L.) [9]

The 4 sphere works well when we assumed a fine structure coupling in i and k , while macroscopically or above the atomic manifold coupling in only j , and sufficiently explains electron interactions at a distance explaining spectral dispersion in hydrogen emissions. This is consistent with the prediction in DSM that the fine structure constant is the cosine effect in j and supports the assumption that its effect exists in both i and k below the atomic manifold. Further evidence of this assumption is when the Octonions are modelled as quaternion pairs and the coupling of the quarks via 4 dimension's made valid quark radius predictions and when calculating the classical electron radius of the electron the fine structure did not come into play.

The transform from GRT to gravity in quantum;

$$r = a_0 = \sqrt[4]{J_B/\pi^2} \times (1/Z\alpha^2) = \sqrt[4]{J_B}/(\sqrt{\pi}Z\alpha^2)$$

Where $\sqrt{\pi}$ is the area of the Gaussian distribution $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-r^2} dr$ and one constituent of quantum blur.

$\sqrt{\pi}r = \sqrt[4]{J_B} \times (\alpha^2/Z) = r \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-r^2} dr$, where $\sqrt{\pi}r$ is one dimension of the taxicab metric. We "Square the Circle" to get the area of the orbital:

$$\pi r^2 = (r \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-r^2} dr)^2 = \ell_p a_0^4 / \sqrt{R_{eff}} (R_{eff})^4 Z^2 = \sqrt{J_B} / \alpha^4 Z^2,$$

predicting the Bohr radius as the most likely orbit in hydrogen. The lemniscate orbit obeys a relativistic Kepler's 2nd law in quantum (conservation of angular momentum), predicted by the WS or intersection of THE & OUR Universe as $0 \rightarrow \infty$ at the BB, since the Bohr model is in terms of gravity rather than electrostatic force or $a_0 = R_{eff}/\alpha = 5.291\ 772\ 108\ 55 \times 10^{-11} m$.

The prediction of additional dimensions as spins about spins is validated by the Octonion spin or quaternion spin about quaternion spin given the Quark radii is a function of 2 cosine effects or α^2 .

3 DSM & GRT: the geometry of Quantum

3.1 How to create a black hole with a let statement

"Black holes are where God divided by zero." Although the saying is often attributed to Einstein, Stephen Wright coined it in a comedy bit, and the discovery of the effective radius of the singularity or $R_{eff} \rightarrow 0$ is the basis of the geometry of space time beneath the event horizon and in DSM, is The empty Universe that existed in perpetuity prior to the creation of OUR Universe with the metric $\overline{AB}_{ijk} = Ct_j + R_{eff} ik$. In lay terms, $R_{eff} ik$ simplifies Quantum to a basic classical understanding when we understand that the physical constants exist on the manifold of the singularity or point particles, when it is understood that the geometry that defines space beneath the atomic manifold or the event horizon is in fact a 4sphere. Hence, Classical mechanics applies beneath the atomic manifold but in 4d while tidal forces on the manifold cause quantum blur or the electron cloud. While the electron has a plastic shell, it is entirely composed of an inner elastic empty space and as such wraps about the manifold of space time much like a balloon would begin to yield to a rigid structure applying a force to its manifold.

Entanglement forces the space-time complementary black hole or EPR Gray Hole. The relativistic force of the spinning space time particle creates a field force where the limit of penetration becomes the event horizon of the point particle and was found to be that of strong force providing a firewall between OUR reality and that of the singularity. The Quantum algorithm is merely an FFT that converts the continuous spin states into a sampled reality. Jason's delta or the singularity delta samples reality at $\mathcal{L}^+ = i \wedge j \wedge k$ and at $\mathcal{L}^- = -i \wedge -j \wedge -k$.

Fig 4 Penrose Diagram with THE Universe embedded

The Penrose diagram, fig 4 demonstrates how the event horizon of matter provides a firewall or ER Bridge, between the

white hole and black hole, and the locally spherical manifold about the outside Universe or THE Universe is $R_s + R_{eff}$, when point particles are modelled as mini Black holes. The ER Bridge can be modelled as a spring and when R_{eff} is maximally compressed to $|\ell_p|$ provided the mechanism for the Big Bangs, the first being a square wave compression yielding full spin particles and the Second Bang a saw toothe compression creating half spin particles. The event horizon, EH, of the PP and its tidal forces blur particles into a cloud about its manifold which can be modelled as a balloon when one considers the space inside as elastic and the manifold as a plastic derivative of compressed empty space. Contained within the event horizon is a 4D spin metric between the manifold of space time and R_s , where $\rho(r) \rightarrow \rho((1/2)\pi^2 r^4)$, and this predicts the classical electron radius, the quark radii and the Bohr radii as the event horizon about space-time using a locally spherical GRT. As such, it is the limit of time, as time becomes complex and locally spherical and presents as matter and j spin converts to i and k spins and these spins manifest themselves as EM.

Contained within the space-time manifold is a taxicab metric and the only measureable distance is $\overline{AB}_i = Ct_j + R_{rap} i$ or $\overline{AB}_{ijk} = Ct_j + R_{eff} i$ in 3D. This let statement can be thought of as the hooks that hold space-time together while R_s is omnipresent on the surface of the manifold of space time as the tidal forces are responsible for the quantum smear of matter about the surface of the waters. The Pauli exclusion principal can also predict the electrons as out of phase by 180 degrees in the same orbit and this was validated in a photonics experiment at Carleton University, where the single slit signature had a correlation factor of 0.9599 with the model when the slits were modeled as 9 wavelength waveguides. It was further validated that the physical traits of the photon exist as the center of mass of the particle anti-particle pair and present as the center of the singularity.[4] A simple CHSH experiment can validate that the origin of the singularity is in fact a third observer in quantum interactions. Further $\overline{AB}_i = Ct_j + R_{rap} i$ regulates the space-time entanglement such that the white hole of space time can radiate information outwards while the black hole consumes information such that the entropy of space-time is $S = A/4\ell_p^2$ from $\partial A = 2G\hbar/C^3 = 2|\ell_p|^2$ or a Planck length squared per dark energy or zero energy photon or particle anti-particle pair, and $\partial R = 4(\ell_p^2/R_{eff})\partial N = 4J_B\partial N$ since in DSM; $\frac{(C)^2 |\ell_p|^2}{R_{eff} m_e} = G$ and $m_e C R_{eff} = \hbar$ and the quiescent energy of the at rest photon is $(3/4)m_e C^2$. Hence when the space-time particle energy is increased from dark energy to a visible photon, the radiated "light" is a function of the space-time black hole as a function of the elastic stretch of its space-time manifold. Space-time is nonexistent inside the space-time particle beyond the one dimensional link between the elastic space of A and B such that $\overline{AB}_i = Ct_j + R_{rap} i/S_p$ where the harmonic spin $S_p \rightarrow h_n$ predicts

a compression of space-time to create half spin particles. Space between the firewall of space-time and extending to the atomic manifold or event horizon of the particle, is a 4 sphere where the gravitational lens of the event horizon demodulates the 4 D phase wave to the one sphere of OUR Universe, much like a holograph while the occluded fronts of i and k and Real spin are encoded in OUR Universe as the electric field and the magnetic field and matter as spinning compressed space-time respectively.

3.2 The Geometry of measurement theory

Greenberger–Horne–Zeilinger, GHZ entanglement exists in fig 5 as ABO, while we (AKA matter) are all entangled with space time where A is the particle or brane, B is the antiparticle or anti-brane and O is the center of the singularity. In essence, pin about 0 is nonrelativistic and is REAL spin in THE Universe, while AB REAL spin is relativistic and AB compresses as REAL spin increases. This entanglement creates a firewall about the singularity. When A and B are maximally compressed by $|\ell_p|$ plus a small amount for plastic deformation, a bang occurs such that A and B move parallel and time stops until equilibrium is reached. The information at the first bang will create a space time particle or black energy with quiescent energy of $(3/4)m_e C^2$ and its gravitational constant $\frac{(C)^2 |\ell_p|^2}{R_{eff} m_e} = G$ as a phantom force about the manifold of space-time. It is noteworthy that time goes stops during the 13 bangs.

Fig 5 A flat static view of the Singularity where j spin is clockwise and k spin is out of the page

The quantum entanglement of the singularity above results as follows:

$$[|\uparrow\uparrow\rangle + |\downarrow\downarrow\rangle] |\downarrow\rangle \rightarrow [|\uparrow\uparrow\uparrow\rangle + |\downarrow\downarrow\downarrow\rangle]$$

With a 1D Boolean representation of OUR Reality resulting.

$$[|AB\rangle + |\overline{AB}\rangle] |\overline{O}\rangle \rightarrow [|\uparrow\uparrow\uparrow\rangle + |\downarrow\downarrow\downarrow\rangle]$$

Given $A = \overline{B}$, WRT to spin, it is noteworthy that entanglement with O means entanglement with the entirety of space time since this point or the singularity, is common to all space time particles, and is a causal link to infinity, as it exist beyond OUR Universe. From a holographic point of view the

origin of the singularity is local to all of space, while it orients about OUR Universe in time, much like 2 radio stations can be physically located in the same place however separated in the frequency or time domain. This may explain why the evaporation of a black hole has an observer entangled with a space-time particle or a radiated photon an infinite distance away in j but locally the same point in i .

There is no standard measure of multi-partite entanglement because different, non-mutually convertible, types of multi-partite entanglement exist, however I suspect that any multivariate system can be reduced to an irreducible binary state in OUR Universe via a 1 sphere, that is of a classical nature, as the multistate is lensed into OUR Reality via the atomic manifold, wherein a state machine exists beneath the atomic manifold, if only in an ethereal sense. Here it is understood the singularity is the wedge sum, WS, of the 2 topologies of quantum and classical space. In a philosophical sense, this state machine is likely consciousness and how Free Will and the Will of the Universe is imposed upon the Classical Laws that exist beyond the atomic manifold. Although GRT and DSM impose a deterministic understanding of OUR Universe as it exists in the quantum world or beneath the atomic manifold, its reality will always be obscured by the uncertainty of a dynamic-time of a sampled reality given: $\Delta x \Delta x/t \geq \hbar/2$, and if x is known the error is imposed on time, Δt . As a personal note I have noted phenologically, that when one surrenders one's Free will to the Will of THE Universe, this sampled reality becomes more manageable, but this is a math paper and as such I have no math for this, so I digress.

The only distance defined inside the black hole singularity is \overline{AB}_i . All other points are an infinite time distance apart as time does not exist inside the black hole. The only info is sent from A to B via R_{eff} in 3D or $R_{rap i}$ in flat space, which is an artifact of $LET \overline{AB}_i = Ct_j + R_{rap i}$. When we use a locally spherical space inside the 4D sphere we see how the line element and 2 +1 or 3 sphere combine to represent the density of space inside the event horizon or beneath the atomic manifold. A further artifact of the Black holes is that there is no speed limit and at the first Big Bang the Real velocity of AB was $C/|\ell_p|$ and G was $1/|\ell_p|^2$ greater than current G. It was in fact the relativistic conservation of momentum that forced the constancy of C in OUR Universe by compressing the radius of Gyration $R_{rap i}$. After the last bang, time equilibrium exists and everything including time is symmetrical about the singularity. $LET \overline{AB}_{ijk} = Ct_j + R_{eff}$ in 3D and half spin particles are the even harmonics of space-time and the Center of mass energy CEM can be calculated via $m_e C^2/2R_{eff}^2$; $E_p = \frac{k_A}{2}(h_n R_{eff} \wedge h_n R_{eff})$ or Planck Einstein as the conservation of C compresses R_{eff} and increases energy via Planck Einstein via frequency $h_n^2 C/4R_{eff}$, where h_n is the harmonic and is consistent with $E = m_e C^2$, for velocities above the speed of light in THE Universe or the singularity while

conservation of momentum is a relativistic effect that compresses the elastic R_{eff} of the singularity.

3.3 The Anatomy of a Black Hole: Unraveling the Hidden Variable within the Singularity's Reff

A black hole possesses two event horizons: an external event horizon and an internal event horizon, also known as the singularity or space-time singularity. The singularity, with an effective radius R_{eff} , is a region where all physical constants become functions of R_{eff} and the properties of the singularity.

This singularity can be conceptualized as a pair entangled black and white holes or EPR Gray Hole. When the entanglement between these two entities breaks down, a particle and/or antiparticle emerges, spinning above the singularity at the event horizon, a position of zero gravity. While the singularity itself remains fixed in the hidden dimension of i , the spacetime system evolves at the speed of light in the time dimension j . This non-local connection between the singularity and the emerging particles highlights the fundamental role of quantum entanglement in shaping the structure and behavior of black holes.

The hidden variable, responsible for determining the properties of the emerging particles, likely exists on the manifold of the singularity where the electron can be modelled as a balloon with a radius of $R_{eff}/2$. Tidal forces from the singularity smear matter about this manifold, creating a cloud of particulates, where the angular position is a function of the wave function and its most likely position is at $\theta = 0$ or the center of mass of the "electron balloon". Reality, as we perceive it, emerges when this smeared matter, such as the electron cloud, is sampled. This suggests a deep connection between the quantum realm and the classical world, mediated by the gravitational forces on the manifold of the singularity and the uncertainty of time within the singularity.

Although this element of uncertainty of time within the theory has no testable pathology, it is consistent with reality and affords a different perspective on research moving forward, as the Copenhagen interpretation dictates a piecewise continuity to reality and DSM predicts a discrete sampled space time, however the discontinuous boundary between sampled time is also continuous but exists in a different dimensionality inside the singularity. Applying a simple z transform to Susskind's holography in light of the entangled white-black hole singularity, should be fruitful.

Fig. 6 Geometry of a Point Particle

The interior event horizon presents as the singularity and is the remnants of the first Big Bang. The singularity or wedge sum, WS, is a white and black hole, or Brane Anti-brane pair, entangled by the morphism, $\overline{AB}_{ijk} = Ct_j + R_{eff}$, R_{eff} being the radius of the 1 sphere firewall about the singularity and the complement of strong force exists on its manifold and this also presents as space-time. The electron, for example, has an event horizon of $R_{eff}\alpha$ or only α times the size of the actual singularity of R_{eff} , which presents as the Classical electron radius, while the Bohr radii or zero g orbital radius is $\frac{R_{eff}}{\alpha}$. It is also noteworthy that the singularity has a circumference of 1 Compton wave length as R_{eff} is the same magnitude of the reduced Compton wave length and encircles THE Universe or space outside OUR Universe. The space between the singularity and the event horizon is a 4 sphere topology and is also the remnants of the first Big Bang. OUR Universe presents as the artifacts of the spin metric defined by $\overline{AB}_{ijk} = Ct_j + R_{eff}$.

The empty space inside the singularity is linked via AB, the only space directive inside the empty elastic space of the singularity and presenting as a wormhole in GRT, so while space time is fixed in AB_i in flat space or \overline{AB}_{ijk} mediating entanglement and predicting a non-local correlation while the entangled system evolves at Ct_j with j spin.

We noted that when the particles were assumed to spin at C and assumed to be a locally spherical space, the classical model of escape velocity converged with the Schwarzschild solution and predicted the classical electron radius, the quark radii and the Bohr radii, as satellite zero g orbits. As such the anatomy of a black hole can be represented in flat space as in Fig. 6.

Space-time beneath the atomic manifold or Event Horizon, R_s , is a 4 Sphere presenting as remnants of the 4D wave equation. Beyond the compressed space at the event horizon a gravitational lens of compressed space demodulates the 4 Dimensional phase wave into a 1D sphere. While the singularity created by the spin of A and B at C creates the wedge sum that links the 2 topologies, the 4 Sphere topology or geometry of quantum space time, exists on its manifold. Geometrically

$A \rightarrow I^F$ and $B \rightarrow I^P$ where geometrically they are static in the i direction yet have a relative motion of C in the j direction or C_j , when j spin is considered the carrier frequency of OUR Universe and is consistent with Schwarzschild de Sitter space-time, with the exception that $A \rightarrow I^F$ and $B \rightarrow I^P$ live on the manifold of space-time, while THE Universe or Infinity exists within the firewall created by R_{eff} since space was inverted during the 13 Big Bangs that stopped time and sealed The compressed Universe inside OUR Universe. This is analogous to blowing up a balloon and tying it off with a Wedge Sum knot.

When we demodulate the j spin the flat fig 6, which can be thought of as spiraling out at C, can be compactified to Schwarzschild de Sitter space-time, where the spiraling out of time is now the height of the cylinder in Fig 3. When we exit the quantum 4 sphere topology through the gravitational lens of plastic deformation that exists on the event horizon of space-time j becomes space time while i, k and R spins become the electric field magnetic field and matter field of compressed space since R exists on the manifold of the event horizon. Hence when we use the volume of a 4 sphere in quantum and volume a 1 sphere in OUR Universe, GRT makes accurate predictions for satellite orbits with respect to the zero g escape radius.

4.1 Significance of ℓ_p in deSitter Space

A 4D phase wave; $\Psi_{ijkR} = \exp[i\omega t] \cdot \exp[j\omega t] \cdot \exp[k\omega t] \cdot \exp[-\omega t] = |\ell_p|$, at the First Big Bang, can be extended to a space time wave via the space time radius $R_{eff}\Psi_{ijkR} = R_{eff}(\exp[i\omega t] \cdot \exp[j\omega t] \cdot \exp[k\omega t] \cdot \exp[-\omega t]) = R_{eff}|\ell_p|$. It predicted the Big Bang at 12.74996082 spins (each spin equals $1m_e$) plus plastic deformation or 12.74996101 and it's second bang that created half-spin particles at 12.24996101 spins, assuming the Compton effect.[5] At the first instant, the maximum compression factor of empty space was $|\ell_p|$ and a further compression of 0.00000019 spins, $1.92949251 \times 10^{-41}$ or $1.19399289 \times 10^{-5}|\ell_p|$ of plastic deformation that forced the Big Bangs.

$$V_{si} \wedge V_{sk} \wedge V_{sj} = 12.24996101_i \wedge 12.24996101_j \wedge 12.24996101_k$$

This is the center of mass energy, CEM of the Proton and Neutron of $(12.24996101)^3 m_e$ 1838.248071 m_e or 939.3428341 MeV is the mass of the Aether and it is the carrier of the proton and neutron and the demodulated space-time energy, when comprised of 2 dimensional quarks form a moment about the CEM. ($a \wedge b = ab$ since $a \cdot b = 0$ before BB)

This is the energy mass of the Aether or space-time, analogous to Quantum Foam & the flat Higgs. The CEM of Aether is 1838.248071 m_e or 939.3428341 MeV.

$$\Delta P / \Delta N = e^{\frac{\pi}{2}}$$

Since in DSM charge is in the i direction, P and N are $\pi/2$ out of phase about the CEM. This predicts a Neutron & Proton mass of 939.565 420 52(54) MeV and 938.272 088 16(29) MeV respectively. It was observed that in DSM, mass increases by $e^{\pi/2}$ for each dimension or $e^{2\pi}$ for each spin due to the compression of space in THE Universe, while the Mass Energy

equivalence due to the constancy of C , increased such that $E = m_e(NC)^3$, where N is the number of spins.

Given the Big Bang in DSM occurs at $|\ell_p|$ in i and k and the assumptions that ds is a function of i and k to arrive at GRT in quantum, the model of space time on the manifold of the Black hole yields an elastic stretch or the manifold of the Black Hole as a function of $|\ell_p|$ as per $\partial A = \frac{2G\hbar}{c^3} = 2|\ell_p|^2$ or a Planck length squared per dark energy or zero energy photon, since in DSM $\frac{(C)^2 |\ell_p|^2}{R_{eff} m_e} = G$ and $m_e C R_{eff} = \hbar$ and the quiescent energy of the at rest photon is $(3/4)m_e C^2$. It is noteworthy that quantum blur smears an incoming photon about the event horizon due to tidal forces which breaks the entanglement, before it is absorbed into the manifold of the event horizon. Hence space inside R_{eff} is separated by compressed plastically deformed space and presents as anti-Desitter space and space outside of R_{eff} is Desitter space.

4.2 Argument for 4 sphere below Atomic Manifold

Although Einstein merely used C^4 in GRT for unit consistency, we argue that it is a residual artifact of the 4 dimensional phase wave that existed before the creation of gravity. $R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}$

$$C^4 \left(R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} \right) = 8\pi GT_{\mu\nu}$$

$$\Psi_{ijkR} = \exp[i\omega t] \cdot \exp[j\omega t] \cdot \exp[k\omega t] \cdot \exp[-\omega t] = |\ell_p|$$

$$\Psi_{ijkR} = \exp\left[\mathbf{i} \frac{Ct}{R_{rap}}\right] \cdot \exp\left[\mathbf{j} \frac{Ct}{R_{rap}}\right] \cdot \exp\left[\mathbf{k} \frac{Ct}{R_{rap}}\right] \cdot \exp\left[-\frac{Ct}{R_{rap}}\right]$$

$$\overline{AB} = R_{eff} \left(\exp\left[\mathbf{i} \frac{Ct}{R_{rap}}\right] \cdot \exp\left[\mathbf{j} \frac{Ct}{R_{rap}}\right] \cdot \exp\left[\mathbf{k} \frac{Ct}{R_{rap}}\right] \cdot \exp\left[-\frac{Ct}{R_{rap}}\right] \right)$$

The velocity wave is such that:

$$\frac{\Psi_{ijkR}}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\overline{AB}}{\partial \tau} = (C_i + C_j + C_k - C_R)\Psi_{ijkR}$$

$$C^4 = (C_i \wedge C_j \wedge C_k \wedge -C_R) \Psi_{ijkR} \text{ and } G = C^2 |\ell_p|^2 / (R_{eff} m_e)$$

$$(C_i \wedge C_j \wedge C_k \wedge C_R) \Psi_{ijkR} \left(R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} \right)$$

$$= 4\pi R_{s\infty}^2 (|\ell_{pi}| \wedge |\ell_{pk}|) \frac{C^2}{R_{eff}} \frac{2}{m_e} T_{\mu\nu}$$

$$(C_i \wedge C_k) \Psi_{ijkR} \left(R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} \right) = 4\pi R_{s\infty}^2 (|\ell_{pi}| \wedge |\ell_{pk}|) \frac{T_{\mu\nu}}{m_e R_{eff}}$$

$$(C_i \wedge C_k) R_{eff} \Psi_{ijkR} \left(R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} \right) = 4\pi R_{s\infty}^2 (|\ell_{pi}| \wedge |\ell_{pk}|) T_{\mu\nu} N$$

This demonstrates the acceleration of space-time to create matter per electron mass m_e , where N is the number of electron masses and where $4\pi R_s^2$ is in units M and is the manifold of space-time in THE Universe in Meters before Big Bang and ℓ_p is the compression factor at first Big Bang or $|\ell_p|^2 \rightarrow m/M$ and $T_{\mu\nu}$ can be thought of as N/Volume or the equivalence of Electron mass density i.e. 4 and 9 for the up and down quarks, where particles are merely harmonic's. This predicts a 4 sphere volume

below the atomic manifold and the values and predicts valid quantum values when the 4 sphere is inserted into Schwarzschild's solution of GRT. This makes GRT fully unit consistent when we consider the first Big Bang occurs at $|\ell_p|$. Given that the Riemann tensor is in m^{-2} , GRT further predicts that space is curved on the manifold of a locally spherical element since m^{-2} is the curvature of a sphere.

The "Resonate frequency of the Aether" is such that:

$$\omega_{LC} = \sqrt{\frac{e^2 Z_c \mathbf{i}}{e^2 Z_L \mathbf{k}}} = \sqrt{\frac{C^2}{4\pi R_{rap}^2}} = \frac{C}{\sqrt{4\pi R_{rap}}} \text{ or } \frac{\omega_0}{2\sqrt{\pi}}$$

The carrier frequency of OUR Universe is $\omega_0 = 5.82258053 \times 10^{20}$ and the resonate frequency of the Aether $\omega_{z0} = 1.64251964 \times 10^{20}$, or $f_{LC} = \frac{1.64365674}{2\pi} \times 10^{20} \text{ Hz} = 2.615960949 \times 10^{19} \text{ Hz}$, just below hard Xray, $3 \times 10^{19} \text{ Hz}$ on the Electromagnetic spectrum. This further evidences the Aether as a transmission medium and the fact that matter is energized Aether, as the Compton effect begins at the soft Xray range or about 10^{18} Hz and the Characteristic Impedance minimizes reflection to 3dB at one decade on either side of the resonate frequency, when the Aether or space time is modelled as a transmission line.

When the "Resonate frequency of the Aether" is written in terms of α , $\omega_{LC} = \frac{\omega_0}{2\sqrt{\pi}} = \frac{3}{8\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{C}{a_0 \alpha}$, we can see that the transfer of information is a function of the Gaussian, $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{x^2} dx = \sqrt{\pi}$, hence consistent with the uncertainty principal, and a_0 which is shown to be the zero gravity satellite radius of the electron when General relativity was normalised to a 4sphere geometry, and given it's derivation, the characteristic impedance is a function of every physical constant.

The rate of change of energy in relative fields can be understood as the relationship between the electric field energy and the magnetic field potential energy:

$$\frac{e^2 Z_c \mathbf{i}}{e^2 Z_L \mathbf{k}} = \frac{(3/4)m_e C^2 \alpha}{m_e 4\pi (\sqrt{3}/2R_{rap})^2 \alpha} \mathbf{j} = \frac{C_i \wedge C_k}{4\pi R_{rap}^2} = \left| \frac{C_i \wedge C_k}{4\pi R_{rap}^2} \right| \frac{1}{t^2} \mathbf{j}$$

This relationship is the nonrelativistic, zero energy Aether in complex time. Adding Real spin in i and k generates the particles via Fourier in Quantum Spin Dynamics and predicts that the real spins are smeared about the nonrelativistic Electromagnetic manifold.

4.3 EPR (Gray) Hole Entropy, the Nascent Universe

Bekenstein-Hawking entropy, BH, was developed such that: $S_{BH} = \frac{A}{4\ell_p^2}$. In this section we show that this is consistent with the 4 sphere assumption of space beneath the atomic manifold for GRT and information per absorbed photon $\frac{\partial N}{\partial R} = \frac{R_{eff}}{4\ell_p^2}$ when the at rest photon mass of the un-entangled positron electron mass predicted by DSM is used and the change in radius of the black hole increases as a function of the singularity radius:

$$\frac{\partial R}{\partial N} = 4 \frac{\ell_p^2}{R_{eff}}$$

The entropy of the Black hole further absorbs the uncertainty of the photon at this rate and the entire interior of the Black hole is THE Universe or undefined empty space with the geometry of a 4 sphere as we will show in this section. Hence the area of the manifold of the black and white entangled hole has 2 undefined spaces, the area inside the spherical EPR Gray hole and the singularities effective radius, R_{eff} on its manifold.

Fig 7 A unit of entropy as predicted by Bekenstein-Hawking entropy.

The issue with the energy derivation in the Susskind lecture[8] at 21:10, is that the photon cannot have any energy relative to wave length since time does not exist on the manifold of a black hole (EPR Gray hole) or as we look at the wave length it becomes infinite at the event horizon. Using the energy of the at rest photon of $E = \frac{3}{4}m_e C^2$ also fails because in DSM the photon is an entangled positron and electron and the tidal forces and monogamous entanglement will not allow the photon or dark energy to prevail on the manifold of the EPR Gray Hole. Hence the energy of the detangled photon increases entropy by $E = \frac{5}{4}m_e C^2$ as we arrive at $|2m_e|$. If we assume the tidal forces on the surface of the EPR Gray hole are huge or 10^{70} times greater than current G in OUR Universe on the manifold which is the boundary between THE Universe or anti-Desitter space and De-Sitter space or OUR Universe and the constant $G = (\ell_p^2 C^2)/(\ell_p^2 R_{eff} m_e)$ exists on the manifold of the EPR Gray hole or WS, then it is reasonable that the entangled electron-positron or the photon at rest mass becomes that of the electron and positron, and further satisfies the monogamy of entanglement in quantum, as the extreme tidal forces overcome the entangled space time or entangled white and black hole and force them to be entangled with the distant Hawking Radiation, the mass of the at rest photon becomes $2m_e$ and as such;

$$\partial R = 2J_B \times 2 = 4 \frac{\ell_p^2}{R_{eff}} \partial N$$

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial R} = \frac{R_{eff}}{4\ell_p^2} \frac{1}{m} \text{ or } \frac{M^2}{m}$$

"It is clear at the outset that black hole entropy should only depend on the observable properties of the black hole: mass, electric charge and angular momentum. It turns out that these three parameters enter only in the same combination as that which represents the surface area of the black hole. One way to understand why is to recall the "area theorem"

(Hawking 1971, Misner, Thorne and Wheeler 1973): the event horizon area of a black hole cannot decrease; it increases in most transformations of the black hole. This increasing behavior is reminiscent of thermodynamic entropy of closed systems. Thus it is reasonable that the black hole entropy should be a monotonic function of area, and it turns out to be simplest such function. $S_{BH} = \frac{A}{4\ell_p^2}$ Where S_{BH} is Bekenstein Hawking Entropy and multiplying by k is the chemist form of entropy." [9]

Hence by adapting to the DSM conversion of GRT to quantum by mapping Area to the effective radius of the singularity $A \rightarrow f(R_{eff})$ or $\frac{\partial N}{\partial R} = \frac{R_{eff}}{4\ell_p^2}$ where ∂N is the number of electron masses or 2 per photon, the above equation becomes the mass energy density function per bit or at rest, un-entangled photon, in flat space or 1 sphere De sitter space, further validating the assumption of a 4 sphere topology in Anti-de sitter space inside the singularity. If A stands for the surface area of a black hole (area of the event horizon), then the black hole entropy, in dimensionless form, becomes a function of the 3D surface area as a function of ∂R and ∂N given:

$$\frac{R_{eff}^3 \partial R}{\partial N} = 4(\ell_p R_{eff})^2 \rightarrow \frac{\pi^2}{2} R_{eff}^4 \partial R = 2\pi^2 \ell_p^2 R_{eff}^3 \partial N$$

This predicts a change in surface area of the Tetrahedron created about the effective radius of the singularity of $4(\ell_p R_{eff})^2$ per photon or bit of information when we view the black hole using information theory, while the $2\pi^2$ represents the involute of the 4 semi-circular lengths of the 4 spin $(i + j + k + R)(\pi^2/2)$ from

$$\Psi_{ijkR} = \exp\left[\mathbf{i} \frac{Ct}{R_{rap}}\right] \cdot \exp\left[\mathbf{j} \frac{Ct}{R_{rap}}\right] \cdot \exp\left[\mathbf{k} \frac{Ct}{R_{rap}}\right] \cdot \exp\left[-\mathbf{R} \frac{Ct}{R_{rap}}\right]$$

or loosely understood as the area of the relativistic tetrahedron convolved through 4 spin, or in lay terms a 4 dimensional arch length when viewed relative to a 1 sphere or flat space. This is consistent with the initial assumption in [5] that space was wound up by the initial Black hole given the involute is merely the arch length of a particle on the extremity when wrapping a piece of string about a sphere and hence the motion of Least Action, as space is compressed about the Void. So the left side is Pre-big bang geometry of 4 D phase wave, Ψ_{ijkR} and the right side is OUR Universe such that:

$$2\pi^2 \partial N \cdot (\ell_p R_{eff_i} \wedge \ell_p R_{eff_k} \wedge R_{eff_j})$$

This indicates that the increase in flat space 3D volume, $\frac{R_{eff}^3 \partial R}{\partial N}$, is a function of the compression factor ℓ_p of compressed space at Big Bang or $4(\ell_p R_{eff})^2$. So while Hawking predicts the entropy to change per photon as a function of $S_{BH} = A/4\ell_p^2$, DSM predicts that the 3D volume as perceived outside the Black and White entangled Black holes is a function of the surface area of the tetrahedron, while the inside is empty space-time and a function of the effective radius of the singularity at maximum compression at which point space is no longer elastic and becomes plastic. Further this confirms that the assumption that space beneath the atomic manifold is a 4 sphere and OUR Universe exists on the manifold as the surface area of the 4 sphere, and this is validated given that this assumption

transforms the energy density tensor in GRT to make valid predictions of Bohr radii, classical electron radius and quark radii as zero gravity satellite orbital radii.

Since the assumption of a 4sphere geometry existing beneath the event horizon and gave valid numerical answers for GRT when used in this domain Berkenstien-Hawking Entropy would be a function of a 4sphere surface area and have a constant $k_{S\infty}$ unit consistent with a 4sphere surface area and unit inconsistency between $|\ell_p| \frac{m}{M}$ and $\ell_p m$: $1/m^3 M^2$ or if the compression factor $|\ell_p|$ is unit less $1/m$.

$$S_{BH} = \frac{2\pi^2 |\ell_p|^2 |R_{eff}|^3}{4\ell_p^2} m^3 M^2 \rightarrow \frac{\pi^2 R_{eff}^3}{2} k_{S\infty}$$

$$\frac{\pi^2}{2} R_{eff}^4 \partial R = 2\pi^2 \ell_p^2 R_{eff}^3 \partial N$$

The left hand side of the equation can be thought of as the rate of change of the density-volume of the 4 sphere since $\partial R \rightarrow \partial N$ where ∂N is the number of electron masses, while the incremental change per photon is the right side and consistent with the let statements impact on the 4 dimensional phase wave at the big bang and this would be expected given that OUR Universe was a Black hole at infancy as predicted by the let statement.

This solution for single bit increments of the black hole as an information storage device, further satisfies the assumption that space below the atomic manifold is a 4 sphere as GRT resultantly predicts the Bohr radii as the zero g orbital radius about the proton as well as the classical electron radius and quark radii relative to the Aether.

Hence the relativistic dimensions of space time beneath the atomic manifold are $\ell_p R_{eff} \mathbf{i}$, $\ell_p R_{eff} \mathbf{k}$, $R_{eff} \mathbf{j}$ and likely a taxi-cab metric with an underlying external algebra, $\ell_p R_{eff} \mathbf{i} \wedge \ell_p R_{eff} \mathbf{k} \wedge R_{eff} \mathbf{j}$ where REAL space exists such that $\mathcal{L}^+ = \mathbf{i} \wedge \mathbf{j} \wedge \mathbf{k}$ plus $\mathcal{L}^- = -\mathbf{i} \wedge -\mathbf{j} \wedge -\mathbf{k} = |\mathcal{C}t|$. The Let statement that creates the Dynamic Spin Metric at a quantum level and predicts QSD or Quantum Spin Dynamics using simple classical physics, via the effective radius of the singularity or R_{eff} and predicts the physical constants on its manifold. It also predicts a Dynamic Space metric in DeSitter space, as an entangled White and Black hole and is fixed in the i direction at $R_{eff} \mathbf{i}$ and expands at Ctj and resultantly, OUR Universe exists in proximity to the Einstein Rosenthal bridge or the wormhole and manifests itself as a hologram as the ER bridge spins at C/R_{eff} , providing the oscillator for the carrier frequency of OUR Universe.

This is further consistent with the assumption that space is a four sphere below the atomic manifold and supports the observation that OUR Universe exists on the surface of the manifold as a 1 sphere; as both allow the Schwarzschild solution of GRT to be used to predict quantum affects such as the Bohr radii as the zero g satellite radii.

5.1 The uncertainty principal in Quantum GRT

While DSM quantises GRT to one electron mass, the tidal forces disentangle the positron and electron on the manifold of the Black hole, hence GRT is quantised relative to 2 electron masses on the boundary between de Sitter space and anti-de Sitter space or the manifold of the singularity. Hence it is simple to see that a huge singularity exists beneath the EPR Gray Hole manifold where space-time does not exist and the singularity likely that existed at the core of the zero energy, is summed, as the tidal forces smear the electron and positron about the manifold of the singularity. Further research will determine whether this "singular uncertainty" prevails on the manifold of the EPR Gray hole that likely defines OUR Universe. Hence from the least action principal, macroscopically, gravity is Newtonian while j spin induces an "error" of η , Eta as prescribed by the wave equation, however we no longer require the cumbersome Schrödinger equation since we can understand j spin in QSD relative to the effective radius of the singularity or R_{eff} . Hence the randomness at a quantum level as prescribed by the least squares solution to Brownian motion maps to a deterministic reality macroscopically given $\delta S_0 = 0$. Given that the effective radius of the singularity does not exist in OUR Universe, δS integrated over the time interval in OUR Universe must distill to $F = ma$, so given at any instant in time, OUR Universe is not deterministic, the path integral in OUR sampled holographic Universe is in fact deterministic. It is therefore, theoretically possible that the Will of THE Universe manifests itself through the uncertainty principal as the uncertainty of the space inside the Black hole increases, while Free Will exists inside the singularity that exists in all point particles as well as the zero energy, black photon or dark energy particle that is entangled about the manifold of the super-singularity and the WS singularities that present as Point Particles.

A logical conclusion, with respect to Freewill, is that the path integral is not affected by Freewill, however quantum effects can alter space-time beyond the frame of reference of the path integral, hence altering OUR perception of the path integral, given the assumption that free will can determine quantum state realisation.

Given that eta must be minimised in the Least action Principal differential equation, $F=ma$ must be satisfied. Hence understanding quantum at a 4 sphere GRT level, we can superimpose the uncertainty principal onto the Least action curve, as the particle spirals about the curve with an effective radius that is that of the singularity or a function of R_{eff}/h_n , where h_n is the harmonic of the particle and $F=ma$ distills to $h_n \frac{(C)^2 |\ell_p|^2}{R_{eff} m_e}$ at a quantum level. Hence macroscopically OUR Universe is deterministic about the oscillation of the singularity given space-time is a sampled reality, however at a quantum level, the interactions occur between sampling of a Holographic Reality and hence the uncertainty principal as a function of R_{eff} must be considered below the atomic manifold where r in GRT is a function of the volume of the 4 sphere, hence adjusting the

energy density tensor of GRT appropriately for a locally spherical space beneath the atomic manifold.

Given that the let statement to initiate the first instance of OUR Universe can be considered to create a metric space of dynamic consciousness, it is a reasonable assumption that consciousness can affect the path integral deviation defined by eta as infinite paths that can be taken by the particles between samples, however the Least Action principal dictates an orbit of fixed radius about the singularity R_{eff}/n as the most probable, hence macroscopically OUR Universe presents as quasi deterministic with a negligible eta as the number of Quantum Dynamic spins about the j increases to what we perceive as a Holographic Reality. The Interior of OUR Universe may be a black hole and the massive uncertainty of this domain is where THE Universe can alter destiny, while the smaller uncertainty about point particles can likely be altered by some essence we have come to know as consciousness. So the current uncertainty of OUR Universe or the Void singularity is currently $8.8 \times 10^{84} \times 4 \ell_p^2 / R_{eff}$ or about $9.19522639 \times 10^{15} \times \hbar$ or $9.19522639 \times 10^{15}$ times larger than the uncertainty of space-time or 1.8×10^{16} times the uncertainty of the electron or $3550.8m$.

At first blush this may seem a trite philosophical analogy, however the Double-Slit Experiment and Quantum Zeno Effect are solid physical evidence that consciousness plays a role in physical outcomes and arguing observation versus consciousness is merely semantics given that a measurement tool is conscious of the laws of OUR Universe, in which it participates in a quantum experiment just as a rock is conscious of gravity and falls to the earth, and further the measurement is a conscious decision of the experimental physicist.

Although this paper furthers Susskind's suspicion that OUR Universe is an entangled black and white hole, this paper indicates that the let there be light photon predicts OUR Universe as an array of entangled white and black holes spinning at the speed of light while the entangled holes grow in the j direction as A and B separate at the speed of light but remain fixed at in i at the effective radius of the singularity, spiraling anti-de Sitter space inside the wormhole and manifesting itself as the manifold of the singularity when demodulated. Hence OUR Universe would have been initially spherical as the super gravity sucked in space to create nascent space-time, and would grow at C along the j axis to become oblong as measured by WSAP.

NINE YEAR MICROWAVE SKY

<http://map.gsfc.nasa.gov/media/121238/index.html> Nine Year Microwave Sky The detailed, all-sky picture of the infant universe created from nine years of WMAP data. The image reveals 13.77 billion year old temperature fluctuations (shown as color differences) that correspond to the seeds that grew to become the galaxies. The signal from our galaxy was subtracted using the multi-frequency data. This image shows a temperature range of ± 200 microKelvin. Credit: NASA / WMAP Science Team WMAP # 121238 Image Caption 9 year WMAP image of background cosmic radiation (2012)

5.2 Nascent Universe versus OUR Universe

Assuming the prior art to be the nascent Universe and an EPR Gray Hole or fundamental Black hole exists at the core of OUR Universe, the Gravitational constant at the first instant would have been $\frac{(C)^2}{R_{eff}} \frac{1}{m_e}$. With the small nascent radius of R_{eff} at $t = 0^+$, for the singularity of the Black hole that mapped THE Universe to OUR current Universe, and the tidal forces would have destroyed any incoming photons to their composite anti-particle particle disentangled masses, transferring the net uncertainty of \hbar of the full spin particle, to the singularity of the growing Void. Hence it is reasonable to assume that the Will of the Universe exists within this non-deterministic void subjecting the core of the Void or super-singularity to quantum effects, while particles about the manifold are governed by the uncertainty principle at a particle level. At steady state of the Universe; $\frac{(C)^2}{R_{eff}} \frac{|\ell_p|^2}{m_e}$, where $\frac{1}{|\ell_p|^2}$ is the number of electron masses in the core of the Universe when a symbiosis is reached or about $3.82807323 \times 10^{69}$ electron masses and would present as dark matter. Nasa currently measured 8.8×10^{84} electron masses for dark matter levels. The nascent gravity of the Void that started at about 10^{70} times would now be weaker than OUR current G, hence as the gravitational pull of the Void decreases OUR Universe will inflate at an increased rate relative to the manifold of the Void. The diminishing gravity of the EPR Gray Hole comprised of zero spin Black Energy (Dark Energy) is the mechanism that varies cosmic expansion and should not be confused with the growth rate of the metric $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 + jCt^2 = 0$, which predicts growth in j at jCt .

The Fine structure constant varies with G, as the Bohr radius and beta function of a dense universe predict; $\alpha = R_{eff}/a_0$ and

given; $\frac{c^2}{r} \propto G$, as a_0 was shown to be the zero g satellite radius of the electron about the proton using 4 sphere geometry in GRT. The fine structure constant α will increase with the age of OUR Universe as G decreases as the radius of the void spinning at C increases. Therefore G_t of the Void decreases from $G_{0+} = \frac{(C)^2}{R_{eff} m_e}$ and the Bohr radius increases in GRT as the zero g electron radius orbit increases and the value of fine structure decreases. This is evidenced by Measurements of the quasar ULAS J1120+0641 where researchers measured the fine-structure constant along a line of sight to the quasar, which is about 12.9 billion light-years away. The measurements combined with other data suggest that the fine-structure constant: Gradually increases as you look further away and gradually decreases as you look closer[10], indicating that the G of the nascent universe was larger, given that GRT in a four sphere geometry predicts the Bohr radii as the zero gravity satellite radii of the electron which will increase as G decreases, given $\alpha = R_{eff}/a_0$. It is noteworthy that the quasar ULAS J1120+0641 observations measured changes in electromagnetic forces back to when OUR Universe was 0.8 billion years old and the wavering G is a causal link to how gravity affects the electromagnetic field via the cosine effect of the Fine Structure constant.

Given the constancy of C, QSD predicts via $\sum_i^4 \overline{LET \overline{AB}}_i = Ct_j + R_{rap}$, that the Void would reach a G equivalent to OUR current value in macroscopic space $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 + jCt^2 = 0$, when the Universes manifold contained $n = 3.82807323 \times 10^{69}$ electron masses or about 9.5 hours in OUR Universe, after the first Big Bang. Given that time stopped during the 13 Bangs, this equilibrium may have occurred during tis period. Black Matter aka Dark Matter and the zero charged form anti-form or particle anti-particle paired manifold now contains 8.8×10^{84} electron masses, so the G of the void is less than the G of macroscopic space and this further predicts that entropy of the Universe will decrease with time in the j direction or Ct_j .

$$\partial R = 2J_B \times 2 = 4 \frac{\ell_p^2}{R_{eff}} \partial N$$

$\partial R = 8.8 \times 10^{84} \times 4 \ell_p^2 / R_{eff} = 2.51693091 \times 10^{12}$ light years of the 4 sphere Void or Super Singularity. Calculating ∂R for the 4 sphere manifold of a 3D surface area; $(2.51693091 \times 10^{12})^{75} \times 2\pi = 12.6 \times 10^9$ as the minimum age of OUR Universe if the Universe is empty. Adding the ordinary matter, assuming it exists in the 3D manifold of OUR Universe, OUR Universe is a maximum of 14.3 billion. Given that the radius of the Void or Super-Singularity has been increasing since the first Big Bang, it would also stretch space-time perpendicular to the j direction as the radius of the 4 sphere increases with the thickness of the 4sphere manifold, creating the Illusion that C has not been constant since the first instance of OUR Universe. This is consistent with NASA observations as is the elliptical "boundary", so given the Universe at any instant in time is a closed set, its expansion implies a "quasi open" set and as such

DSM can predict a topological space that is fixed or closed at any instant given $D = Ct$, but open as at the next instant in time as it is larger by $C\Delta t$, and this further advances Susskind's holographic principal as space-time in DSM is sampled with each spin of the Universe, and what we perceive as reality is the demodulated j spin. Fig. 5

The geometry of the core or super-singularity of OUR Universe is predicted by DSM to be a 4 sphere and anti-de Sitter space while the 3D manifold is a 1 sphere in j and presents as a 3D space given its existence on the Manifold in 3D. The AdS/CFT defines the relationship of space below the atomic manifold which is also shown to be 4 sphere geometry, with respect to GRT. Hence the curve of space viewed from within the atomic manifold is $\Omega_0 < 1$ and $\Omega_0 > 1$ when viewed from OUR perspective and likely contained within the boundary or gravitational lens of plastic deformation, $\Omega_0 = 1$, making Ω_0 relativistic.

It is a reasonable conclusion that space in OUR Universe, which exists in 3D on the Manifold of the 4 sphere Super-Singularity is a 1 sphere and OUR Universe is expanding at Ct_j 'ab initio saeculi' and this is evidenced by using the volume of a 1sphere of $2r$ to adjust the energy density tensor and normalise the Schwarzschild solution such that it predicts the zero g satellite radius in OUR Universe. The 4 sphere volume normalises GRT for reality below the atomic manifold and given that this apparent radius of the super-singularity, at the first instance accurately predicts the age of OUR Universe, it is worthwhile furthering its predictions to discover the Utility and simplicity of a Dynamic Space Metric, DSM and the utility of Quantum Spin Dynamics, QSD, given that the effective radius of the singularity that exists inside point particles simplifies our quantum understanding of the Universe so us dumb ass engineers can build stuff with it.

5.3 Proper Atomic time at Event Horizon

I can only speak parenthetically, but I suspect that Einstein's God did not throw dice, as he proclaimed and as such Free will and what we perceive as the Will of THE Universe, were what he envisioned for mankind. Although quantum encapsulates a distribution of events that occur at the same time and we can only know which one will present as a matter of chance, does not make any logical sense and given that the Universe is based on fractal evolution of simple constructs, why would one accept the lack of logic to explain the quantum world? DSM was able to insert GRT seamlessly into quantum, by monitoring how the electron warped empty space around it and then assumed that the coupling effect to matter in GRT is $\widehat{\alpha k} \wedge \alpha i = \alpha^2 j$. Hence, as a function of the diminished gravitational flux about the atomic manifold, the Bohr radius is developed, not by the electrostatic forces used by Bohr, but the gravitational forces or escape radius of GRT, AKA event horizon, or zero g and proper time relative to the electron. This was a function of the electron's mass imposition upon its own space-time relative to the Aether as

evidenced by Schwarzschild's empty space solution to GRT. Further DSM explains the quantum effects introduced by the Rydberg constant, $R_{eff}/4\pi a_0^2$ as the relationship between the effective radius of the Aether and the manifold of the atomic manifold.

To develop gravity at a quantum level we assumed end of proper time to be complex time of the particulate that creates the massive electron and that of the electron relative to the Aether, which we have come to know as space time.

The compressed space that is statically compressed due to the plastic deformation of the BBs likely creates some type of lensing caused by the inversion of time forcing the 4 dimensional phase wave known as matter into a single phase. This is also known as the photon, creating a one sphere universe that presents as flat. The real part of the phase wave Ψ_{ijkR} is stored on the manifold of space-time or the PP, as the constancy of C forces time to compress on the manifold as per $\exp[-\omega t] = |\ell_p|$, while the direction of time or the photon or space time is $i \wedge j \wedge k$ macroscopically. In macroscopic space, DSM uses j as the direction of time and hence one must be cognizant of $\pi/4$ phase shift in i, j, k .

The first BB created 1 spin particle's and space time or the Aether. Hence the classical radius of the electron as the second harmonic exists smeared about the space time bubble or Aether, mapping directly to the manifold of space time and predicted by GRT as the escape radius of the electron particulate from the locally spherical Aether when OUR Universe is assumed to spin at C, and the plastic deformation is also smeared about the manifold of the Aether. This is the first gravitational lens of the plastically deformed space and reduces the 4 D phase wave to a 2 D, $i \wedge j, j \wedge k$ or $i \wedge k$ as basis vectors for quarks and $i \wedge j \wedge k$ with a static or scalarish j for the electron. The following relationship was shown to predict the separation of the particulate from the Aether to become the electron.

My intuitive, if not colloquial, understanding of quantum is that it is developed from the perspective of the Electron, hence a relativistic quantum gravity would require complex proper time from the perspective of the electron, and this hunch seemed to work out quite nicely.

So from the perspective of OUR Universe time stops at the quantum event horizon, but from the perspective of the quantum world, it is just beginning to tick properly or tick spherically. See spherical time. This perspective, from the Atomic manifold into the quantum world via the gravitational lensing of the 2 lenses of the gravitational flux, creates a quantum blur. Understanding how this lensing affect, affects the math of quantum, will make this field of some utility to us dumb ass engineers.

This becomes evident when we use the 4 sphere to transform the r of Schwarzschild's solution to GRT, which works below the Atomic manifold yet requires the 1 sphere for GRT to work macroscopically in GPS.

Simply put, the dice part of quantum is more simply and logically understood as the Gaussian distribution of the electron orbits (assumed to be random in quantum), and the Bohr radii as the whole of events that exist within the manifold of the uncertainty principal or R_{eff}/h_n where h_n is the harmonic of time imposed upon each particle, where the even harmonics are half spin particles and 1 spin are the odd harmonics. In this example N=2 for the electron while N=1 electron mass was used for the GRT solution of the Bohr radii.

6.0 Conclusion

A simple let statement; $\sum_1^n LET \overline{AB}_i = Ct_j + R_{rap} i$ forces spin

$$\Psi_{ijkR} = \exp[i\omega t] \cdot \exp[j\omega t] \cdot \exp[k\omega t] \cdot \exp[-R\omega t]$$

When the REAL part or compression factor of this 4D phase wave equals $|\ell_p|$, the big bang creates full spin particles at the First Bang and half spin particles at the second bang and a myriad of particles in the remaining 11 Bangs, such that the following macroscopic metric, $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 + jCt^2 = 0$, prevails as a dS topology and its Aether has a center of mass energy CEM.

Within the event horizon a 4D AdS topology exists with a plastically deformed space-time boundary, where it presents as a point particle or WS on its manifold. Although both the dS space and AdS spaces are curved the manifold or WS presents as locally flat. The discovery of the effective radius of the WS of R_{eff} simplifies quantum in terms of classical physics and QSD prevails as a model that appears to link Quantum, GRT, LQG and string theory. When the core of OUR Universe is modelled as an EPR Gray Hole, the decreasing gravity on the Black Matter Manifold, AKA dark matter, as it increases in size, explains the dS expansion as the gravitational bond of ordinary matter in OUR 4sphere manifold Universe, decreases.

Since DSM is invertible and energy deficits are stored in the elastic Aether, any point in the Aether can be understood as the reference frame for an infinite number of frames of reference.

Although OUR Universe is infinitely continuous yet bounded, and time is piecewise continuous and the sample rate of OUR Universe is at the gamma ray frequency boundary, DSM predicts a holographic Universe. The boundary between

quantum and macroscopic space time is that of a wedge sum, WS manifold, which is the boundary between the two; anti-Desitter space at a quantum level and macroscopic Desitter space topologies and the physical constants are classical physical equations that exist on its manifold and these we are gifted, via the splendors of Creation when we take the time to enjoy the gifts of nature and some of the beautiful people THE Universe has created for us to enjoy.

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